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Bringing European Building Policy to Life

Energy Performance Certificates: Development of EPC Policy Guidelines for Greece

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CONTENTS

	Executive summary	02
	List of abbreviations and acronyms	03
	List of figures.....	03
	List of tables	03
1	Introduction	04
	1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable.....	04
	1.2 Structure of the deliverable.....	04
	1.3 Interactions and inferences between EPCs and other policy instruments	05
2	Methodology	09
	2.1 Approach for developing EPC policy guidelines.....	09
	2.2 Data collection and analysis.....	10
3	Policy needs and status quo of EPCs in Greece	12
	3.1 Policy needs and priorities.....	12
	3.2 Current EPC system: opportunities for development.....	13
4	EPC policy guidelines for Greece	15
	4.1 Policy options and scenario for improvement.....	15
	4.2 Details on implementation of high priority measures.....	18
	4.2.1 What is foreseen in the EPBD?.....	18
	4.2.2 What has the country already done in relation to the measure(s)?.....	20
	4.2.3 What can be done?	21
	4.3 Proposed action plan and first steps.....	23
	4.4 Monitoring and evaluation of EPC schemes	25
5	Conclusions, recommendations and next steps	27
6	References.....	29

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents key policy measures and recommendations for energy performance certificates (EPCs) in Greece, within the framework of the EPBD.wise project. The overarching aim is to improve energy efficiency in the building sector, focusing on compliance, methodology refinement and digitalisation to align with national and EU objectives, based on the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).

The methodology used for each focus country was to first identify its policy needs, the types of intervention called for, and the priorities and policy measures required to address them. For Greece's EPC system, policies are needed on design and rescaling, communications and perception, training and auditor capacity, the database, and quality control.

Key recommendations for Greece are as follows

- Strengthen EPC quality control by updating the TEE KENAK software so it interacts more effectively with the national database, ensuring data consistency, and introduce periodic independent audits to reinforce the reliability of EPCs.
- Reinvest in and enhance mandatory training for EPC auditors, supported by a communications campaign aligned with national legislation.
- Improve EPC design to be clearer, more user-friendly, and capable of integrating the smart readiness indicator and renovation passport.
- Update the calculation methodology to base EPCs on a numeric indicator of primary energy use per unit of reference floor area per year.
- Enhance public awareness and acceptance of EPCs via targeted campaigns, and establish one-stop-shops to assist building owners and promote the value and use of EPCs.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

DBL	Digital Building Logbook
DGEG	Directorate General for Energy and Geology
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HES	Home Energy Scotland
MEPS	Minimum Energy Performance Standards
MS	Member State
NBRP	National Building Renovation Plan
NZEB	Nearly zero-energy building
RP	Renovation Passport
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
ZEB	Zero-Emission Building

List of figures

Figure 1	Data collection and analysis for EPC policy guidelines development	11
Figure 2	Greece's EPC front page layout	21

List of tables

Table 1	Interactions between EPC and other EPBD policy elements.....	08
Table 2	Policy priorities and measures for Greece	13
Table 3	Greece's policy gaps identified and EPBD opportunities	14
Table 4	Greece's specific measures to be implemented, suggested country pathway and responsible entities	18
Table 5	EPBD requirements related to Greece's measures	19
Table 6	Implementation status of measures and obligations.....	20
Table 7	Status quo of EPBD Annex V requirements for EPC front page layout.....	22
Table 8	Greece's EPC policy improvement stakeholders list and roles	23
Table 9	Greece's proposed action plan	24
Table 10	Policy needs categorized by intervention type, per country.....	27

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable focusses on specific policy guidelines for each of the focus countries for which national partners defined EPCs as a priority under the EPBD-wise framework: these are Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary and Poland. The main objective is to assess different options for improving the EPC schemes in these countries under the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requirements. This assessment is based on the extensive work carried out in previous EPBD-wise tasks, namely the mapping of policy needs for each country and the identification of good practices in a wide range of topics such as communication and perception, quality control, expert training and qualification, database use and calculation methodologies, among others. The policy guidelines will consider different approaches based on best practice examples and the specific conditions in the target countries, reflecting the current status of their EPC systems along with any ongoing or planned modifications.

This document focuses on Greece, and provides detailed policy guidelines for the development and improvement of its EPC system under the EPBD framework.

An initial attempt to define priority action plans is also developed by pinpointing priority interventions selected from the range of policy guidelines. Each roadmap outlines the steps required, ensuring a clear and actionable path forward as well as defining the specific stakeholders and their roles in this process.

The main aim of this deliverable is to match policy objectives with policy needs and mandates, particularly focusing on the EPBD. Specific policy needs can be addressed more effectively by leveraging the transposition of the EPBD. They will also be grouped to streamline the process and prepare the ground for replication.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Besides this introductory chapter which outlines the objective's structure and links with other policy elements of the EPBD, there are three main sections in this deliverable:

The methodology section describes the approach used to develop the Policy Guidelines, including the methods used to collect and analyse data. It then focuses on the policy needs and the current implementation status of EPCs in Greece.

Next, the document presents EPC policy guidelines for Greece. It outlines the opportunities for development in the current EPC system framework, and proposes options and scenarios for improvement. An action plan with initial steps is provided, along with a monitoring and evaluation framework that Greece can apply to ensure the ongoing effectiveness of EPC schemes.

The last chapter details the main conclusions and recommendations for Greece, and provides a short comparative cross-country analysis of policy gaps and opportunities to establish a replicable framework.

1.3 Interactions and inferences between EPCs and other policy instruments

The EPBD introduces significant changes to the framework for EPCs across Member States. A harmonised classification system from Class A to G must be implemented by 29 May 2026 (derogations apply), where Class A corresponds to zero-emission buildings (ZEBs) and Class G identifies the worst-performing buildings in the national stock. Member States that already apply an A0 class for ZEBs may continue this designation, with adjustments to the rest of the scale. The distribution of Classes B to F should ensure a suitable reflection of the national building stock while respecting the EU-wide framework, allowing differentiation by building types (residential/non-residential) and climatic zones. An additional A+ class can be included voluntarily, and is applicable to buildings that have an energy demand 20% lower than the ZEB threshold and that generate more renewable energy on site than they use.

Member States that have rescaled their EPC schemes between 1 January 2019 and 28 May 2024 may defer the new classification requirements until 31 December 2029 to preserve stability in national systems. EPCs must express energy performance as a primary energy indicator kWh/(m².y) and include other indicators such as operational greenhouse gas emissions and on-site renewable energy use. While certain indicators are mandatory, Member States may add voluntary ones such as detailed splits by type of use and building element details, carbon removals, number and type of recharging points for electric vehicles, or smart readiness. EPCs must also have a uniform visual identity nationally, be machine-readable and accessible, and include clear recommendations on energy performance improvement, emissions reductions, and indoor environmental quality.

Affordability is addressed by encouraging Member States to implement measures such as cost caps or financial support for vulnerable households. Quality control provisions require that at least 90% of EPCs are statistically valid and that a minimum of 25% undergo third-party verification when controls are delegated to non-governmental bodies, with the possibility of reducing this share as system reliability improves. Simplified EPC update procedures must be in place when minor improvements or renovation passport measures are implemented.

EPCs remain valid for 10 years, but new certificates must be issued at key trigger points, including construction, major renovation, sale, rental or contract renewal. Display obligations are expanded to cover all public buildings and non-residential buildings frequently visited by the public, regardless of size. These measures aim to improve EPC transparency, comparability and reliability across the EU while allowing flexibility for national adaptation.

In addition to the legal and technical requirements established in the EPBD and its respective guidance documents^[1], the development of EPC systems across Member States can be further guided by the strategic insights provided by the NextGen EPC Cluster, which consolidates outputs from nine Horizon 2020 projects focused on next-generation EPCs^[2].

This cluster recommends positioning EPCs as a central, user-friendly and interoperable tool in the building decarbonisation agenda, in line with broader EPBD provisions such as minimum energy performance standards (MEPS), ZEBs, renovation passports and digital building logbooks. Key recommendations include:

- Harmonised calculation methodologies: Adoption of a shared core ('kernel') calculation logic based on EU standards (e.g. CEN standards under Mandate M/480), promoting comparability and transparency across Member States.
- Additional focus on non-renewable primary energy, to allow fair comparison across different energy systems and technologies.
- Integration of measured data (e.g. from smart meters or indoor environmental quality sensors) to complement or validate calculated performance, helping to reduce the performance gap and better reflect actual building behaviour.
- Dynamic and user-centric EPCs: Certificates should evolve from being static compliance documents into interactive tools that reflect renovation progress, are updated with real-time data, and are integrated with renovation passports, digital building logbooks and the smart readiness indicator.
- Enhanced quality assurance and training: Establishment of harmonised protocols for third-party verification, continuous training and certification of EPC assessors, and rigorous validation of input data.
- Actionable and forward-looking recommendations: EPCs should provide structured renovation guidance aligned with deep renovation principles and long-term decarbonisation pathways (e.g. target Class A or ZEB by 2050).
- Broader indicator coverage: Certificates should progressively integrate indicators related to indoor environmental quality, smart readiness, carbon performance and climate resilience.
- Full digital interoperability: EPCs must be machine-readable and interoperable with national and EU-level building databases, enabling streamlined integration with public policy tools and financing schemes.

These recommendations support the EPBD's objective of making EPCs a central pillar in planning, implementing and monitoring energy renovation strategies at building, district and national levels, while also enhancing reliability, usability and public trust in the certification process.

EPCs have an intrinsically pivotal role in several elements of the EPBD, most notably the ones that are directly addressed by EPBD-wise: EPCs can be used to **check compliance with MEPS**, and they work hand in hand with building **renovation passports** – they can be issued jointly and renovation passport improvement measures can replace EPC recommendations in certain cases. The ZEB definition is intrinsically connected with the EPC, since **EPC labels are built on evenly distributed scales that will always mean a ZEB is Class A**.

When defining **national building renovation plans (NBRPs)**, one crucial aspect is the **definition of the very worst-performing buildings**. These must **correspond to EPC Class G**, which gives the EPC a central role in defining national trajectories for residential building stock, as well as its role in defining minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) for the non-residential sector, which can use thresholds directly linked to EPC classes. In parallel, EPC registers and databases provide a unique, harmonised source of information on the building stock, enabling Member States to map the distribution of energy classes across dwelling types and regions, identify renovation needs, and quantify the shares of worst-performing buildings and energy-poor households. This data infrastructure allows NBRPs to set evidence-based trajectories, monitor progress over time against intermediate milestones (e.g. reductions in the share of Class G and F buildings), and update policy measures as new certificates are issued, thus turning the EPC into a continuous feedback and monitoring tool rather than a one-off compliance document. It is also instrumental in ensuring that the most vulnerable consumers are correctly addressed, as most of them are likely to be living in the worst-performing buildings. EPC-based data can support the targeting and tracking of social measures and dedicated support schemes in line with the EPBD requirements to prioritise the worst-performing and energy-poor households.

EPCs are also critical as part of the monitoring, reporting and verification of EPBD related initiatives as they are the **core part of the data to feed the energy performance of buildings database**. These databases are essential for actions across a variety of different levels, as depicted in the EPBD:

- 1 At the building level, since the data stored will allow easy and free-of-charge access to the full EPC (which includes the identification of energy performance improvement recommendations) for building owners, tenants and managers.
- 2 At the neighbourhood level, for example as a support tool for initiatives related to energy communities and citizen-led initiatives.
- 3 At the city/regional level, by providing local authorities with access to data on the energy performance of buildings in their territory (for instance, to facilitate the drafting of heating and cooling plans).
- 4 At the national level, as this information should be anonymised, made publicly available, coherent and interoperable with other national building databases. It should also be used to better plan, monitor and implement public policies and financing mechanisms.

Furthermore, **EPCs have a role in ensuring adequate funding is in place and aligned with the long-term targets**, and that barriers related to high upfront costs – especially on vulnerable consumers prone to energy poverty – are addressed and prioritised. This can be done at the building level by incorporating renovation passport features and information aligned with the 2050 decarbonisation target and the needs and expectations of building owners, managers and users. EPCs are also a useful tool for providing support to financing schemes pinpointing concrete renovation measures at the building level, as well as for informing, driving and monitoring building renovation policies and funding schemes.

Finally, **EPCs take the lead role in the communication of building energy performance**. EPCs are the key source of information on all aspects related to this metric. They can – and should – include additional indicators and data on subjects such as greenhouse-gas emissions and global warming potential, capacity to provide demand response to the grid, carbon storage and removal, building smartness, and indoor environmental quality.

The following table summarises the interactions between EPCs and other EPBD elements, and the policy directions these imply:

Policy Instrument / Element	Functional Level	Primary Function	Interaction with EPCs	Policy Implications
Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS)	Regulatory Enforcement	Define and enforce minimum energy performance thresholds for buildings	EPCs can be used to check compliance with MEPS; energy classes (A-G) can be directly linked to MEPS thresholds	EPCs operationalise MEPS by providing measurable, comparable performance data for enforcement
Renovation Passports (RP)	Building-Level Execution and target alignment	Provide stepwise renovation roadmaps for individual buildings	EPCs can be issued jointly with RPs; RP improvement measures may replace EPC recommendations in some cases	EPCs and RPs together guide and track deep renovation, aligning building upgrades with policy targets
Zero-Emission Buildings (ZEB)	Strategic Benchmark	Set the highest energy performance standard (Class A)	EPC energy classes are anchored to ZEB definitions (Class A corresponds to ZEB); EPCs signal ZEB achievement	EPCs communicate ZEB status and progress, supporting national and EU decarbonisation goals
National Building Renovation Plans (NBRP)	National Strategy	Define national trajectories and targets for building stock	EPCs identify worst-performing buildings (Class G) and track progress towards NBRP targets	EPCs provide data for planning, monitoring and reporting under NBRPs
Digital Building Logbooks (DBL)	Data Integration	Aggregate building data for policy and financing	EPCs are integrated into DBLs, providing standardised, machine-readable performance data	EPCs enable interoperability and data-driven policy/funding decisions
Quality Assurance & Control	System Reliability	Ensure reliability and validity of EPCs	EPCs are subject to independent control systems, third-party verification, and statistical sampling	EPCs' credibility and policy impact depend on robust quality control
Financial Support & Affordability	Social Equity	Support vulnerable households and promote uptake	EPCs may trigger financial support; affordability measures are linked to EPC issuance and recommendations	EPCs help target and monitor financial support, ensuring equitable policy implementation
Public Information & Awareness	Communication	Raise awareness and promote energy efficiency	EPCs serve as the main communication tool for building energy performance, including greenhouse gases, global warming potential, and renovation options	EPCs drive public engagement and informed decision-making

Table 1 – Interactions between EPC and other EPBD policy elements

This document explores the opportunities that are open to Greece for effectively addressing the policy needs it has identified, complying with the new EPBD requirements and ensuring the EPC system can contribute to the strategic setting defined above.

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology used to define the policy guidelines for the effective use of EPC schemes in the focus countries. This includes previous work on the specific policy needs, gaps and good practices identified for the countries in question, and the opportunities that the new EPBD may offer.

2.1 Approach for developing EPC policy guidelines

The development of EPC policy guidelines started with the mapping of policy needs and best practices, which involved gathering insights from various sources. Initially, insights were drawn from previous EU projects, national initiatives, direct stakeholder engagement, and a thorough review of relevant literature. This comprised a combination of desk research, stakeholder interviews and workshops. Stakeholder interviews at the national level were planned to identify the specific challenges faced in each country. Additionally, collaborative workshops held during policy forums developed by the EPBD.wise project helped to facilitate dialogue among experts, policymakers and stakeholders, fostering the exchange of ideas and the identification of key challenges and policy requirements. While the primary focus of the project is on the six designated countries – i.e. Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Ukraine – it was nevertheless also crucial to consider its broader implications across the EU.

Therefore, the compilation and analysis of policy needs extend beyond these focus countries, ensuring a comprehensive understanding with potential applicability across EU Member States. To survey and identify policy needs, a questionnaire was distributed to the six countries selected in the EPBD.wise project, allowing respondents to select the most important topics for further development. The results of both questionnaires have been used to identify policy needs in each focus country.

A second stage involved the identification of best practices to help meet the key policy needs identified, with examples retrieved from various EU countries. These examples generally address several challenges, including poor governance due to insufficient collaboration among different levels of government, staff shortages in public administrations, and data-related issues such as availability and quality. In the construction industry, labour and skill shortages, along with fragmented supply chains, hinder workforce capacity and investment.

The previous two steps are further detailed, including all the results and conclusions for each focus country in^[2]. This is the first report from the EPBD.wise project, titled “Energy Performance Certificates: Policy needs and best practices”.

Following the initial mapping, the selection was further streamlined by determining which of the countries selected EPCs as a priority for development. On this basis Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary and Poland were chosen as the target countries for advancing with detailed policy guidelines. The overall process for selecting and analysing focus countries, contact points, inputs and further research is depicted in Figure 1 (see Section 2.2 Data collection and analysis).

2.2 Data collection and analysis

As has already been stated, one of the main sources for these policy guidelines was the first EPBD-wise deliverable related to EPCs, namely “Energy Performance Certificates: Policy needs and best practices”^[2]. Figure 1 below illustrates the overall process, which began with data analysis performed under this framework including desk research, the questionnaire answered by each focus country, and interactions with focus countries in meetings and policy forums.

The next step included a fine-tuning of the best practices in light of specific EPBD opportunities for the country analysed and its planned implementation pathways, and the creation of tailored country questionnaires based on the policy needs identified in the previous step and on additional interactions with focus countries.

In the final step, the policy options, priorities and action plan were peer-reviewed by EPBD-wise partners, contact points in the focus countries, and other stakeholders. The final version of the policy guidelines includes their feedback.

Based on the results of the first two stages of the project, especially on the specific policy needs for the four focus countries, additional questionnaires were developed that included the following subjects:

- 1. EPC rescaling and calculation methodology**
- 2. EPC databases**
- 3. Training and education of experts**
- 4. Quality control mechanisms**
- 5. Integration of other indicators/schemes with EPCs**
- 6. EPC recommendations**
- 7. Communication and perception**

The questionnaires provided the basis for the interviews and informed additional data-gathering when required. The main objective was to delve deeper into each policy need, assess the current status of the EPC system in relation to it, scrutinise current planning and activities related to the EPBD transposition, identify the main stakeholders, and pinpoint what kind of short-term actions could be leveraged and proposed.

Figure 1 – Data collection and analysis for EPC policy guidelines development

POLICY NEEDS AND CURRENT STATUS OF EPCs IN GREECE

In this chapter, a summary of the main policy needs identified in the previous work under EPBD.wise is presented, together with a first prioritisation.

3.1 Policy needs and priorities

In Greece, EPCs are mandatory for most property transactions (sales, rentals, new constructions and energy renovation projects), and the EPC class must be clearly stated in all real estate advertisements. The scheme is centrally managed by the Ministry of Environment and Energy through its energy inspection departments, with a centralised EPC database (www.buildingcert.gr) where certified engineers manually input building data and the system calculates emissions using national software based on a monthly, semi-static methodology (ISO 13790 E2:2009) applied consistently to both residential and non-residential buildings.^[3]

The EPC methodology was last updated in 2017, and there is ongoing debate about simplifying the procedure, although some argue the current ISO-based approach is already streamlined. Renovation passports are seen as complementary rather than as integral, to avoid overloading the EPC while leveraging synergies with existing schemes. Since 2016, any qualified engineer can issue an EPC after an energy study, without needing to have received specific EPC training, leading to concerns about quality despite there being a sufficient supply of experts. Public perception is generally negative in the residential sector (EPCs are seen as a cost with little useful information), while service buildings value EPCs more when they are linked to technical reports or audits. Stakeholders welcome efforts to improve interoperability between the EPC database and renovation passports, although there is currently no one-stop-shop to improve access to information and solutions and to boost public trust.^[3]

In summary, Greece’s EPC system faces significant challenges related to EPC design, communication and perception, training/auditor capacity, and quality control.

Greece’s policy priorities and measures				
Priority	#1	#2	#3	#4
Greece’s policy priorities	Improve EPC design and rescale	Improve public perception of EPCs	Reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors	Strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms
Policy need category	EPC design/ rescaling	EPC communication/ perception	Training and auditor capacity	EPC quality control/ database
Intervention type	Technical/legislative and regulatory	Information and perception	Technical	Technical/legislative and regulatory

Table 2 – Policy priorities and measures for Greece

Although all aspects of the main policy needs are addressed in each country, this prioritisation exercise was crucial for developing the policy improvement scenarios detailed in Chapter 4. It helped to define and focus on the first steps of the action plan, and to identify relevant stakeholders for prioritised actions.

3.2 Current EPC system: opportunities for development

Policy priorities are measures or actions identified for each policy need. In this section, the aim is to explore how the opportunities identified in the EPBD can help to address policy priorities and needs.

Policy priority # 1 – Improve EPC design and rescale: In the EPBD, opportunities for the design of the EPC include the introduction of a scheme for renovation passports, as well as issuing the two together (in which case the passport can replace the improvement recommendations in the EPC) or separately. Another opportunity is the implementation of a smart readiness indicator. Regarding rescaling, the EPBD requires an A to G scale, with A for zero-emission buildings (ZEBs) and G for the worst stock performers, ensuring balanced B to F distribution and an optional A+ sub-level (this will apply from May 2026, extendable to 2029 for post-2019 rescales); new templates will also apply from May 2026, including for primary energy kWh/(m².y), greenhouse gas emissions, and life-cycle global warming potential for A-rated renovations.

Policy priority # 2 – Improve public perception of EPCs: Programmes to provide information, training and raise public awareness should be developed by local and regional authorities. Setting up mandatory one-stop-shops with the criteria defined under Articles 18 and 19^③ of the EPBD^[4] and in accordance with the guidance in Commission Notice C/2025/6438 is a reliable opportunity for improving public perception^[1].

Policy priority # 3 – Reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors: The EPBD requires that EPCs and inspections be carried out by qualified or certified independent experts. It obliges Member States to ensure their certification, to make public lists of such experts, and to promote training and education to ensure a sufficient and competent workforce in the construction and energy renovation sector.

Policy priority # 4 – Strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms: Member States must provide a clear definition of the quality objectives and the level of statistical confidence that the EPC framework should achieve. The independent control system should ensure that at least 90% of issued EPCs are valid with 95% statistical confidence. The validity of the input data must be verified with information provided by the independent expert through on-site visits (which may be carried out by virtual means, where appropriate) in at least 10% of the EPCs that are part of the random sampling used to assess the overall quality of the scheme. Member States may use different strategies to detect and target poor quality in EPCs in order to improve the overall quality of the scheme.

Table 3 summarises Greece’s specific policy needs (as identified in “Energy Performance Certificates: Policy needs and best practices”^[2]), the country’s current planning, and the opportunities identified in the EPBD.

Policy needs for effective EPC systems design	Current planning	EPBD opportunities
EPC design	In line with EPBD transposition (TBD)	Member States must introduce a scheme for renovation passports and may allow for them to be drawn up and issued jointly with the EPC. The smart readiness indicator should be implemented. Rescaling and new indicators are needed.
Low public perception of EPCs	In line with EPBD transposition (TBD)	Local and regional authorities should be consulted and involved in the development of programmes to provide information, training and awareness-raising. Member States should prepare and carry out information and awareness-raising campaigns.
Lack of training	In line with EPBD transposition (TBD)	Promote training courses for experts.
Lack of quality control	In line with EPBD transposition (TBD)	Member States must provide a clear definition of the quality objectives and the level of statistical confidence that the EPC framework should achieve. The independent control system must ensure that at least 90% of EPCs issued are valid, with a statistical confidence of 95%. The validity of the input data should be verified with information provided by the independent expert. The validity of the input data should be verified by on-site visits, which may be carried out by virtual means, where appropriate, in at least 10% of the EPCs that are part of the random sampling used to assess the overall quality of the scheme.

Table 3 – Greece’s policy gaps and EPBD opportunities

EPC POLICY GUIDELINES FOR GREECE

Key policy options and measures for Greece include improving EPC design and rescaling (**Policy priority # 1**), improving public perception of EPCs (**Policy priority # 2**), reinvesting and enhancing training for EPC auditors (**Policy priority # 3**), and strengthening EPC quality control mechanisms (**Policy priority # 4**).

These priorities align with EPBD requirements while addressing specific weaknesses in the current Greek system. Integration with ongoing initiatives such as iBRoad2EPC^[3] and the smart readiness indicator programmes^[4] offers opportunities to enhance both technical performance and stakeholder acceptance.

4.1 Policy options and scenario for improvement

Policy priority # 1 – Improve EPC design and rescale

To address the rescaling challenges, Greece should transition its calculation methodology to assess buildings based on absolute primary energy use expressed as kWh/(m².y), as mandated by Article 19.1 of the EPBD. This shift from the current reference-building approach to an absolute metric will provide clearer, more comparable performance indicators. Rather than implementing a complete system overhaul, Greece should refine the existing ISO-based methodology to address critical gaps, particularly the significant divergence between estimated and metered energy use, which currently undermines trust in EPC accuracy. It should be remembered that, according to the common general framework for the calculation of the energy performance of buildings (Annex I of the EPBD), the influence of the behaviour of the occupants must be factored out of the calculation.

Regarding rescaling, Greece will need to adjust the EPC scheme so that Class A corresponds to ZEBs as defined in the EPBD, Class G represents the worst-performing segment of the national building stock, and Classes B–F are consistently distributed between these two endpoints, with the underlying primary energy thresholds and the certificate template aligned to the new common EU framework.

Alongside methodological improvements, Greece should incorporate the renovation passport and smart readiness indicator into the EPC framework, and rescale energy classes to align with the EPBD's A to G classification system. The country has already taken initial steps through SRI pilot projects supported by the LIFE programmes SRI-ENACT, easy SRI, Smart Square and SRI2MARKET^[4], providing a foundation for full integration^[4].

Policy priority # 2 – Improve public perception of EPCs

Some Greek municipalities are interested in having one-stop-shops to improve public perception of EPCs and better communicate their benefits, but there are two barriers: insufficient funds, and the lack of a coherent national strategy to support such an endeavour. The EPBD could provide the boost that one-stop-shops need under a national mandate through the provisions of Article 18 (one-stop-shops for the energy performance of buildings). However, complementary pathways could also be adopted, such as campaigns to improve public perception of EPCs, integration of financing models, or communications tailored to renovations and where the information is available.

Policy priority # 3 – Reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors

Reinstating and improving training programmes for EPC auditors could also be an option for Greece: supported by a communications campaign targeting auditors, training could be made mandatory under national legislation.

Policy priority # 4 – Strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms

To strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms, the Ministry of Environment and Energy or the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources (CRES) could develop a web version of the TEE KENAK software (or create an add-on), in the same way as other providers of private software tools for EPC preparation have done, such as Easykenak. This would provide additional information on the interpretation of the geometrical features from the auditor. EPCs can already be recalculated, as the XML file for the calculation already has to be uploaded by the energy auditor. However, without a visit to the property it is not possible to check if the energy auditor has done their job accurately. Periodic independent audits could also help to ensure the consistency and quality of EPCs.

These measures are not only technically feasible but they are also strategically important for Greece's broader energy policy objectives. The following section outlines how each priority measure relates to other policy elements, how it supports EPBD compliance, and how it contributes to national decarbonisation goals.

Links with other policy elements

The improvement of EPC design aims to make EPCs clearer and more user-friendly, ensuring that key information – such as energy ratings, renovation recommendations and additional indicators – is easily understood by building owners, tenants and policymakers. Additionally, this measure includes the incorporation of renovation passports and the smart readiness indicator into the EPC framework, ensuring a more comprehensive assessment of buildings' energy performance and digital readiness. This aligns with EPCs' role as a primary tool for communicating building energy performance, and supports informed decision-making at various levels, from individual buildings to national databases.

Enhancing public perception of EPCs is crucial for reinforcing their role in renovation passports and financing schemes. Improving public awareness ensures that EPCs are effectively used to guide renovation strategies. A better understanding of EPCs also helps to promote energy-efficient renovations, especially among building owners who may be hesitant due to high upfront costs. This measure supports the broader EPBD objective of ensuring that vulnerable consumers, who are more likely to live in the worst-performing buildings, have access to clear and actionable information about energy improvements.

Reinvesting in and enhancing training for EPC auditors strengthens EPCs' reliability in verifying compliance with MEPS and monitoring NBRPs. High-quality audits ensure that EPCs provide accurate energy assessments, making them a trustworthy tool for tracking energy efficiency improvements. Well-trained auditors also play a key role in identifying energy-saving opportunities and ensuring that EPC recommendations align with long-term decarbonisation targets. This measure supports the EPBD's monitoring, reporting and verification functions, ensuring that EPC data accurately reflects the energy performance of buildings at the national level.

Strengthening EPC quality control mechanisms through an improved database further enhances their credibility and usability. A robust database ensures that EPC information is accurate, up-to-date and easily accessible for building owners, policymakers and financial institutions. This aligns with the EPBD's requirement for EPC data to be anonymised, publicly available and interoperable with other national building databases, facilitating better planning, monitoring and implementation of energy policies. Additionally, a reliable EPC database supports the identification of worst-performing buildings, helping to set priorities for renovation strategies and funding allocation.

Measure	EPBD requirements	Country-specific pathway	Responsible for policy implementation
Policy priority # 1 Improve EPC design and rescale	Member States must introduce a scheme for renovation passports and may allow for these to be drawn up and issued jointly with the EPC. Member States may voluntarily implement the smart readiness indicator.	Make EPCs clearer and more user-friendly, and integrate the smart readiness indicator and renovation passports into them. Change the calculation methodology to ensure more reliable and easier-to-apply results for engineers. Rescale the EPC.	Ministry of Environment and Energy
Policy priority # 2 Improve public perception of EPCs	Local and regional authorities should be consulted and involved in the development of programmes to provide information, training and raise awareness. Member States must prepare and carry out information and awareness-raising campaigns.	Launch campaigns to improve public perception of EPCs. Couple with one-stop-shops to integrate financing models. Communications should be tailored to renovation projects and clearly indicate where and how building owners can access further information and support.	Ministry of Environment and Energy
Policy priority # 3 Reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors	Promote training courses for experts.	Implement mandatory training. Implement a targeted communication campaign aimed at engineers who should attend the training, clearly linking the benefits and content of the course to the applicable national legislation.	Ministry of Environment and Energy, Academia
Policy priority # 4 Strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms	To ensure the quality of EPCs, renovation passports, smart readiness indicators and of the inspection of systems, an independent control system should be established in each Member State.	Update the TEE KENAK software to improve data consistency. Run periodic independent audits to help ensure consistency and quality of EPCs.	Ministry of Environment and Energy

Table 4 – Greece: specific measures to be implemented, suggested country pathways and responsible entities

4.2 Details on implementation of high-priority measures

This chapter presents a selection of priority measures which have the strongest potential to address key challenges. Each measure is described and analysed in detail, with particular attention to its implementation pathway, expected benefits, and role within the broader policy framework. The aim is to provide practical and actionable insights into how these measures can be translated into effective action.

4.2.1 What is foreseen in the EPBD?

The EPBD mandates that Member States should adopt a standardised EPC template and a common visual identity within their territory that ensures clarity, comparability, and relevance of information. The directive requires EPCs to include a common classification system based on an A to G scale, with clear representation of primary and final energy use, operational greenhouse gas emissions, renewable energy production, and other relevant indicators as stipulated in Annex V. Member States are encouraged to integrate supplemental elements such as renovation passports and the smart readiness indicator into the EPC framework, enabling certificates to evolve from static documents into dynamic tools guiding building renovations and smart building readiness assessments.

The EPBD establishes a common framework for the methodology to calculate the energy performance of buildings (Article 4 and Annex I). The calculation must be based on the typical energy consumption for various uses (heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting etc.) and must express performance through a quantitative indicator in /year in primary energy, ensuring transparency and comparability. Article 19 further mandates that the EPC must show the building's energy performance with a clear numerical indicator grounded in this methodology.

For the rescaling, the EPBD mandates a common A to G scale, where A (or A0 if Member States have already adopted A0 to designate ZEBs) denotes ZEBs and G the worst performers in the national stock at implementation, ensuring balanced distribution across B to F classes (or A to F where A0 designates ZEBs), with an optional A sub-level of A+ for buildings with a 20% lower energy threshold than a ZEB and that generate more renewable energy on site annually than their total annual primary energy demand. EPCs must adopt the new template by 29 May 2026, with countries that rescaled after 1 January 2019 and before 28 May 2024 allowed an extension to 31 December 31 2029.

Recognising that the effectiveness of EPCs depends largely on their acceptance and use by stakeholders, the EPBD explicitly calls for Member States to implement public awareness and education campaigns coordinated at national, regional and local levels. These initiatives should target building owners, occupants, market actors and vulnerable groups to enhance understanding of the benefits associated with EPCs, including their role in driving energy renovations and accessing financing. To facilitate this, the EPBD mandates the establishment of one-stop-shops across Member States, which act as centralised support points offering technical advice, administrative assistance and financial guidance to building owners during renovation processes. These one-stop-shops help to overcome common barriers related to complexity, perceived costs and trust issues, thus playing a crucial role in improving public perception and the practical implementation of EPCs.

Together, these provisions within the EPBD establish a strong legislative foundation for Greece to enhance EPC design and foster positive public perception.

EPBD requirement	Summary
Standardised EPC design	EPCs must follow the EPBD standardised template with an A to G classification scale; clearly show primary/final energy use, GHG emissions, renewable energy, and other Annex V indicators; and integrate renovation passports and the smart readiness indicator for dynamic, actionable information.
Data interoperability and digitalisation	EPCs should be digital, machine-readable, interoperable, and accessible to building owners, tenants, professionals, and policymakers for transparency and usability.
Calculation methodology	There should be a common and transparent methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings, based on typical energy consumption for various uses and expressed as a clear numerical indicator of primary energy use in kWh/(m ² .y).
Public awareness	Greece must implement coordinated awareness and education campaigns targeting building owners, occupants, market actors and vulnerable groups, focusing on EPC benefits such as renovation guidance and access to financing.
One-stop-shops	Establish one-stop-shops as central support points providing technical advice, administrative help and financial guidance during renovations; one-stop-shops address complexity, cost and trust barriers, improving EPC acceptance and use.

Table 5 – EPBD requirements related to Greece's measures

4.2.2 What has the country already done in relation to the measure(s)?

The current Greek EPC calculation method applies a semi-static monthly approach according to ISO 13790, which does not use dynamic simulations and does not capture effects such as system automation, building mass, or free cooling. The building's energy class is determined by comparison with a national reference building, rather than as expressed by a numeric indicator of primary energy use. The methodology lacks full integration of the EPBD's new instruments such as the smart readiness indicator and renovation passports. A significant gap exists between estimated and actual energy consumption, which could impact the reliability of – and trust in – EPCs if it is not properly frameworked and communicated. Greece has initiated pilot projects to test the smart readiness indicator, supported by LIFE projects, and made some moves towards EPC digitalisation and centralised databases, but a fully aligned methodology according to the updated EPBD, particularly one where energy performance of buildings is expressed by a numeric indicator of primary energy use in kWh/(m².y) rather than relative values, is not yet in place.

Efforts are also focusing on rescaling the EPC energy classes to align with the EPBD labelling system, though this requires careful communication to avoid negative public perceptions. In the current Greek EPC scheme, energy performance is expressed on an A to G scale, where class A indicates the most energyefficient buildings and class G the least efficient, with intermediate classes (B, C, D, E, F) defined by national primaryenergy thresholds and shown as coloured bars from green to red. What is problematic under the new EPBD is that these national thresholds were set before the recast requirements, so class A is not yet explicitly tied to the ZEB definition and class G is not calibrated to represent the worstperforming share of the national stock, meaning the existing scaling will have to be recalibrated.

Regarding public perception, EPCs in Greece currently face challenges with low acceptance and negative attitudes, especially among residential building owners who see EPCs largely as administrative burdens rather than as valuable tools for saving energy – the Greek authorities and other stakeholders recognise the critical need for public awareness campaigns and educational initiatives. While no national one-stop-shop system currently exists, municipal interest in establishing one-stop-shop platforms is high: these could serve as integrated hubs for technical advice, financial guidance and EPC-related support, directly improving

EPBD obligation or measure	Implemented in Greece?	Notes	Deadline
Integration of smart readiness indicator and renovation passports	No	Smart readiness indicator and renovation passport elements not yet included: these are the subject of active policy discussions and technical planning.	– (not mandatory)
Calculation methodology update	No	The building's energy class is determined by comparison with a national reference building, rather than as a numeric indicator of primary energy use.	– (not mandatory, still it should be coherent with the numerical approach in kWh/(m ² .y) referred to primary energy)
Public awareness and perception	No	Low acceptance and perceived administrative burden; coordinated public campaigns and educational initiatives are needed.	– (initial targets)
One-stop-shops	No	No national one-stop-shop platform exists; there is strong municipal interest, but funding and coordination are required to launch integrated support hubs.	29 May 2026

Table 6 – Implementation status of measures and obligations

4.2.3 What can be done?

To improve its EPC design, Greece should focus on updating its EPC framework to fully align with the requirements of the EPBD by 2026. This includes updating its EPC calculation methodology in line with Article 19 of the EPBD, adopting the primary energy indicator expressed in kWh/(m².y) to ensure transparency and reliability. Efforts could focus on narrowing the gap between estimated and real energy performance by incorporating metered consumption data, and on establishing clear frameworks and communication tools to effectively bring the EPC closer to citizens' needs and expectations.

Greece should also integrate missing indicators such as the smart readiness indicator and renovation passports into its EPCs, transforming static certificates into dynamic renovation tools. Simplifying the format of the EPC to improve clarity and usability will also help to foster understanding among building owners, tenants and professionals. Greece should invest in digitalising EPCs further to ensure they are machine-readable, interoperable with national databases, and easy to access. This digital transformation will help overcome current limitations and enable better monitoring and policy evaluation.

Regarding rescaling, Greece can recalibrate the numerical primary energy thresholds for each EPC class so that A aligns with the national ZEB definition and G is anchored to the worstperforming segment of the stock, redistributing B to F accordingly. In parallel, the EPC template can be updated to match the common EU format: clear communication and guidance given to market actors (including examples of 'old vs new' ratings) can help avoid confusion and rebuild trust in the rescaled labels.

To improve public perception of EPCs, Greece should implement coordinated national, regional and local awareness campaigns highlighting their direct benefits, such as guiding energy renovations and easing access to financing. These campaigns should target vulnerable groups, building owners, occupants and market actors with tailored messaging to overcome the misconception that EPCs are mere administrative burdens. Establishing and funding one-stop-shops is crucial, as they provide centralised and trusted support offering technical advice, administrative facilitation and financial guidance to building owners throughout renovation projects. One-stop-shops will help address common barriers related to complexity, perceived costs and trust, thereby increasing EPC acceptance and enhancing their effective use.

Figure 2 – Greece’s EPC: front page layout

Below in Table 7 is an analysis of what Greece will need to change on the front page of its EPC, in accordance with Annex V of the EPBD.

EPBD requirements (front page)	Present in EPC?	Notes
Energy performance class	Yes	Need to rescale by 29 May 2026
Calculated annual primary and final energy use in kWh/(m ² .y) and kWh or MWh	Yes	Clear indication of primary energy use in kWh/(m ² .y) plus reference building approach adapted and inspected if applicable; final energy building approach
Renewable energy produced on site (% and total, main energy carrier)	No	Not indicated
Operational greenhouse gas emissions in kgCO ₂ /m ² /year	Partial	CO ₂ emissions presented; global warming potential and full operational greenhouse gas details missing
Calculated energy needs in kWh/(m ² .y)	No	Not documented or not broken down by system and use on the first page of the EPC
Capacity to react to external signals (yes/no)	No	Not indicated
Heat distribution system capable for low or more efficient temperature levels, where applicable (yes/no)	No	Not indicated
Contact information of the relevant one-stop-shop	No	Only certifier's contact details are included; no mention of a one-stop-shop

Table 7 – Status of EPBD Annex V requirements for EPC front page layout

4.3 Proposed action plan and first steps

This section comprises two tables that list the stakeholders and their respective roles in EPC improvement (Table 8) alongside a suggestion of an action plan (Table 9). The good practices that can add value to the measures are also referenced. Further details on these good practices can be found in the EPBD.wise report Energy Performance Certificates: Policy needs and best practices^[3].

Stakeholder name	Category	Role	How to be involved
Ministry of Environment and Energy	Government	Implementing and managing new policies	Meetings, workshops, emails, content development, policy validation, communication
Technical Chamber of Greece	Energy experts	Supporting implementation of new policies and providing technical expertise	Meetings, workshops, emails, technical expertise, data provision
INZEB	Energy experts	Supporting implementation of new policies and providing technical expertise	Meetings, workshops, emails, technical expertise, data provision
Universities and other educational institutions	Academia	Organising training for auditors	Training, workshops
Finance sector	Business/Government	Finance training; providing financial support for vulnerable households	Financing schemes
Real estate sector	Business	Adapting the real estate market to the new policies	Integrate EPBD minimum standards
Independent energy consultants	Energy experts	Providing technical expertise	Meetings, workshops, emails, technical expertise, data provision

Table 8 – Greece’s EPC policy improvement stakeholders and their roles

Priority	Objective	Key activities	Good practices	Responsible for policy implementation	Expected outputs	Timeline
Policy priority # 1 Improve EPC design and rescale	Improve the accuracy and usability of EPCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update calculation methodology to use a numeric indicator of primary energy use kWh/(m².y) Integrate renovation passports and smart readiness indicator Rescale 	D5.1 – Denmark’s Owner-Oriented EPCs (Good Practice No. 6)	Ministry of Environment and Energy, Technical Chamber of Greece, INZEB	Reliable and transparent EPCs; higher user trust	29 May 2026
Policy priority # 2 Improve public perception of EPCs	Increase the perceived value of EPCs and renovations among owners and tenants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create awareness campaigns and one-stop-shops presenting the benefits of EPCs, linking them to incentives for renovation 	<p>D5.1 – Scotland’s HES one-stop-shops (Good Practice No. 5)</p> <p>D5.1 – Denmark’s owner-oriented EPCs (Good Practice No. 6)</p>	Ministry of Environment and Energy, Technical Chamber of Greece, INZEB	Increased uptake of EPCs and renovations	Continuous
Policy priority # 3 Reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors	Promote effective adoption of new EPC methodology and terminology by ensuring widespread, mandatory participation in auditor training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch mandatory training Launch targeted communication to engineers highlighting new terminology and the necessity of training, focusing on compliance with national law 	D5.1 – Sweden’s EPC expert training (Good Practice No. 1)	Ministry of Environment and Energy, universities and other educational institutions	Higher participation in training; improved EPC quality	Continuous
Policy priority # 4 Strengthen EPC quality control mechanisms	Raise the overall reliability of the EPC process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a web-based TEE KENAK tool or plugin, similar to Easykenak, to assist auditors with data Implement periodic independent audits involving on-site or virtual property visits to verify inspection accuracy 	<p>D5.1 – Portuguese quality assessment system (Good Practice No. 2)</p> <p>D5.1 – Ireland’s quality assurance (Good Practice No. 3)</p>	Ministry of Environment and Energy, Technical Chamber of Greece	Improved EPC accuracy and consistency, and increased public trust in certification	29 May 2026

Table 9 – Greece’s proposed action plan

Timeline for implementation of measures under the EPBD

The deadlines indicated for each priority in Greece’s action plan reflect the timetable for transposing and implementing the new EPBD, but they are also calibrated to Greece’s starting point. The more structural measures – EPC design improvement and rescaling (**Policy priority # 1**) and strengthening EPC qualitycontrol mechanisms (**Policy priority # 4**) – are aligned with the deadline of 29 May 2026 laid down in the EPBD for full implementation of the revised requirements on EPC content, classification, databases and control systems, meaning they should be defined by that date to ensure compliance.

Priorities that rely mainly on capacity-building and behavioural change – such as improving the public perception of EPCs (**Policy priority # 2**) and enhancing training for EPC auditors (**Policy priority # 3**) – are framed as ongoing actions, since they demand continuous skills development, repeated engagement with engineers and building owners, and gradual adaptation of messages and tools as the Greek EPC framework and market conditions evolve.

4.4 Monitoring and evaluation of EPC schemes

Effective monitoring, reporting and evaluation are essential to ensure that EPC schemes fulfil their central role within the EPBD. As emphasised in the EPBD.wise report An Integrated MR&E Framework for Effective EPBD Implementation, EPCs are not merely compliance documents but pivotal datagenerating instruments for tracking progress in renovation, energy performance, zeroemission pathways, and policy coherence across the building sector. Key points for EPC schemes include:

Monitoring: Ensuring that EPC data – including energy classes, primary energy indicators, operational greenhouse gas emissions, recommendations and building characteristics – are continuously collected, validated and fed into national databases. These databases must integrate EPCs with inspection data, renovation passports, the smart readiness indicator, and measured building consumption where available.

Reporting: Member States must ensure transparent, harmonised annual reporting to the national building performance database and the EU Building Stock Observatory. This allows EPCbased indicators to inform NBRPs, MEPS implementation, ZEB uptake, and financial planning at national and EU levels.

Evaluation: Evaluation checks the extent to which EPCs are providing actionable insights. The EPBD.wise monitoring, reporting and evaluation framework recommends that this should include:

- the quality and statistical validity of issued EPCs (quality control);
- the effectiveness of EPC recommendations in triggering renovations; and
- the impact and support provided by EPC schemes on policy objectives such as MEPS and trajectories compliance, energy poverty alleviation, financing schemes and progress toward ZEBs.

Best-practice examples from other focus countries include the following:

Portuguese quality assessment system: Ensuring the quality and reliability of EPCs through rigorous verification processes, qualified experts meticulously examine data and information recorded by EPC assessors to ensure accuracy and compliance with established criteria and methodologies. The Directorate General for Energy and Geology (DGEG) promotes confidence among stakeholders (including building owners, real estate agents and policymakers) by ensuring the reliability of the EPC database. The Portuguese energy agency ADENE's approach involves a systematic review of EPCs to verify the correctness of energy performance indicators, the appropriateness of the selected calculation methodologies, and compliance with national and EU regulations. This system's effectiveness is enhanced by close and effective communication with experts, focusing on error prevention rather than penalties, through proactive monitoring and the accompaniment of assessors during building visits. This could be a good approach for Greece to implement, as it requires quality control and a database that reflects the real state of the building stock. However, it does raise issues such as how to guarantee reliability and independence, as well as increased costs.

Ireland's quality assurance risk-based approach: This provides guidelines and performance criteria to assessors, ensuring their competency and upholding the credibility of EPCs. Continuous monitoring and stakeholder engagement enhance EPC quality control. The Irish system involves comprehensive checks on EPC data, assessment methodologies, and compliance with national and EU standards. Feedback mechanisms have been established to improve the performance of assessors and maintain the accuracy of the EPC database. As with the previous good practice, Greece could significantly benefit from this approach to improve the quality control of its EPCs and database..

Portugal's EPC financing: This serves various stakeholders and objectives by providing tailored recommendations, taxation benefits and financial incentives to promote energy efficiency initiatives. Portugal's EPCs play a pivotal role in incentivising renovation actions, facilitating access to funding schemes and supporting comprehensive energy efficiency improvements. By integrating various policy objectives into the EPC framework Portugal addresses multiple needs, including EPC recommendations, database management, and the integration of other indicators and schemes. Using EPCs as a gateway to financing could be a way of improving public perception in Greece. With this approach, Greece could benefit from an improved database that is more representative of the building stock.

United Kingdom EPC quality control: UK EPCs have quality control guidelines to ensure accuracy and consistency. Energy assessors are required to maintain comprehensive records for each EPC they produce. These records should include data files or software data collection forms that detail the information used in the EPC calculation, allowing quality assurance assessors to verify the accuracy of each data entry stage associated with the Simplified Building Energy Model or Dynamic Simulation Model. Additionally, design documents such as floor plans, elevations and sections should be retained to facilitate EPC recalculations if necessary. Site notes, whether in paper or electronic format, are also essential components of the documentation. For Greece, this good practice could help in providing reliable and standardised data on a building's energy performance, which is a significant gap in the country's current EPC system. Another key opportunity is to increase consumer and stakeholder confidence by making EPCs a trusted tool for property owners, tenants and investors.

CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND NEXT STEPS

A comparative analysis of the policy needs across the focus countries enables a clearer understanding of the context, preparing the ground for replication of good practices and highlighting areas for each country to build upon.

The next table is an update of a similar summary exercise that was published in the EPBD-wise report on Energy Performance Certificates: Policy needs and best practices^[3], including the results of recent interactions with focus countries and additional data provided.

Intervention type	Policy needs	Bulgaria	Greece	Hungary	Poland
Technical/Legislative and regulatory	EPC rescaling and calculation methodology	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technical/Legislative and regulatory	EPC quality control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Information and perception	EPC communication/perception	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technical	EPC databases	Yes	No	Yes	No
Technical/Information and perception	EPC recommendations	No	No	Yes	Yes
Technical/Legislative and regulatory	Integration of other indicators/schemes with EPC	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Technical	Training and auditor capacitation	Yes	Yes	No	No

- Policy needs **identified as priority** from the start of the EPBD-wise process
- Policy needs that have **shifted priority** between the *EPC Policy needs and best practices* and the *EPC Policy Guidelines*
- Policy needs that were not identified as priority

Table 10 – Policy needs categorised by intervention type, per country

The main priorities for all countries included are related to the technical, legislative and regulatory, and information and perception aspects of EPCs. More specifically, policy needs in all the countries concern the methodology for rescaling and calculating EPCs, quality control mechanisms, and communication and perception.

The summary table above also shows that although most countries did not identify core issues regarding the methodology for rescaling and calculating EPCs as policy needs in the first step, these aspects were subsequently highlighted when the requirements of the EPBD were analysed. This also reflects the importance of these two major changes in the EPBD and the fact that, in most cases, rescaling and new mandatory indicators for calculating EPCs and defining MEPS and national trajectories will require significant methodological changes. This should be seen as a trigger point for other interventions, for instance in setting up improved databases and to boost wider communication strategies. These conclusions and common priorities define a first framework for replicating the policy guidelines in additional countries.

As Greece's approach and pathway focus on improving EPC design, enhancing training for EPC auditors, updating the calculation methodology, and quality control, it can provide useful insights for other countries. One such example is the proposal to include additional indicators and take advantage of ongoing EU-financed projects to leverage this approach. Extensive experience and data have been collected from projects dedicated to renovation passports and the smart readiness indicator. The need to increase data exchange and facilitate the work of the auditors by providing web-based solutions is also worth highlighting as an approach for replication, in line with the EPBD's recommendation to make EPCs affordable and to ensure ease of data exchange.

In summary, Greece should focus on strengthening EPC quality-control mechanisms by improving interactions with the national database through updates to the TEE KENAK software to ensure better data consistency, alongside the introduction of periodic independent audits to reinforce reliability. There is need to reinvest and enhance training for EPC auditors, with mandatory training supported by a communication campaign for engineers aligned with national legislation. The design of EPCs should be improved to make the certificates clearer, more user-friendly and capable of integrating both the smart readiness indicator and renovation passport elements. The calculation methodology needs to be updated so that EPCs are based on primary energy use kWh/(m².y), refining rather than overhauling the current method. Finally, Greece should improve the visibility and acceptance of EPCs through targeted awareness campaigns and by establishing one-stop-shops to assist building owners and to promote understanding of the value and utility of EPCs.

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